

On the Pyrolysis of Thiuram Disulphides

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Pyrolytic decomposition of tetraethyl, N, N'-diethyl-N, N'-diphenyl- and N, N'-dimethyl thiuram disulphides has been investigated. In addition to the earlier reported products, the tetraethyl thiuram disulphide is found to afford ethylene and 1,1,3-triethyl thiocarbamide. The main features of decomposition are analogous in all cases. The results have been discussed.

TETRAMETHYL- and tetraethyl thiuram disulphides and tetramethyl thiuram monosulphide are well-known rubber vulcanization accelerators. As such, their thermal decomposition is of considerable interest. Koch¹ and Sahasrabudhey and Radhakrishnan^{2a} have reported such studies and have outlined detailed mechanism explaining formation of various products. In the case of tetraethyl thiuram disulphide(I), the main products reported are: elemental sulphur, carbon disulphide, diethylammonium diethyldithiocarbamate(III), tetraethyl thiocarbamide(IV), monosulphide(II) and small quantities of tetraethyl thiuram disulphide(I) which probably arise as a secondary reaction product.

Formation of these several products excepting III is easy to understand from the mechanism proposed by the above workers. No explanation has, however, been offered about the source of non-ethylenic hydrogens of III which is a major product^{2b}.

On reinvestigating the decomposition at 140-50, a yellowish red liquid distilled out as reported

earlier and a part of which solidified on cooling. On examination, this was found to consist of all the products stated above (*vide supra*) and in addition 1, 1, 3-triethyl thiocarbamide(VI) and small quantities of tetraethyl thiuram disulphide(I). Examination of the gaseous products revealed the presence of ethylene(V) and in traces of hydrogen sulphide. While hydrogen sulphide can be regarded as a side product often associated with the decomposition of sulphur compounds, formation of the other two new products, *viz.* ethylene(V) and triethyl thiocarbamide(VI) needed to be explained. The small quantities of I could arise either by aerial oxidation of III or could have been carried during distillation along with other products. The pot residues were also found to contain triethyl thiocarbamide(VI) amongst other products.

Independent experiments showed that tetraethyl thiuram monosulphide(II) did not decompose appreciably at the above temperature of pyrolysis and it is therefore concluded that it could not be an intermediate under the present reaction conditions, between I and the other decomposition products,

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The cyclic mechanism for the elimination of ethylene and other changes as envisaged above [route 3, changes (i) to (iv)] have been confirmed by pyrolysis of N, N'-diethyl-N, N'-diphenyl thiuram disulphide(IX) where also ethylene is found to be formed along with the other expected products *viz.*

elemental sulphur, carbon disulphide, N, N'-diethyl-N, N'-diphenyl thiuram sulphide(X), N, N'-diphenyl-N-ethyl thiocarbamide(XI) and trace amount of thiocarbamide(XII). These changes can be shown as in scheme [4 (i)-(v)].

where Ph = phenyl.

to IV and VI. The spot which did not run was probably due to III.

On chromatographing the above distillate (0.5 ml) in a column using Silica Gel (BDH grade) and benzene-acetone (70 : 30) as eluent various fractions were collected. The first fraction (6 ml) was found to contain a mixture of I, thiuram monosulphide(II) and IV when co-chromatographed with the authentic samples on a TLC plate using benzene : acetone (90 : 10) as solvent system. Further separation of I and II could not be achieved as their R_f 's were very close in all solvent systems. Second fraction (10 ml) was found to contain pure 1,1,3-triethyl thiocarbamide(VI). The solvent was distilled out under reduced pressure when VI was obtained, m. p. 45°. m.m.p. with an authentic sample of VI, 45°. Further confirmation was obtained by its co-chromatography with the authentic sample, when a single spot was obtained $R_f=0.47$ in benzene : acetone (90 : 10). Further fraction (15 ml) gave a yellowish semi-solid compound (TLC, $R_f=0.5$, benzene : acetone 70 : 30) which could not be identified. The remaining fraction on evaporation in vacuum afforded a solid, m.p. 75°. On reprecipitating it from its alcoholic solution by petroleum ether (60-80°), it gave a white crystalline solid, m.p. 83°. It was identified as III through its undepressed m.m.p. with an authentic sample.

Paper chromatography of the mercuric acetate solution on Whatman No. 1 using ascending technique and propanol^a : triethylamine : water (50 : 25 : 25) medium gave two spots on development with diphenyl carbazide. The blue spot with R_f 0.73 was identified as due to ethylene(V) when compared with an authentic sample prepared by the action of zinc on ethylene dibromide⁴. The spot which had not run at all was probably due to mercuric acetate. TLC of the above solution in the same medium as above also gave a bluish-white spot due to ethylene with diphenyl carbazide, R_f 0.713.

The alkali solution on acidification liberated hydrogen sulphide.

Pyrolysis of Tetraethyl Thiuram Monosulphide(II) :

II (4 ml) was found to be stable at 140-50°. However, on increasing the temperature to 210°, a pale yellow liquid started distilling out, a part of which solidified in the condenser. The solid, m.p. 80°, was identified as III (m.m.p. 80°). TLC of the distillate (benzene : hexane ; 70 : 30) gave spots for I through IV and VI as were obtained in the pyrolysis of I. The gaseous products were found to contain hydrogen sulphide and ethylene.

Pyrolysis of N, N'-diethyl-N,N'-diphenyl Thiuram Disulphide(IX) :

N,N'-Diethyl-N,N'-diphenyl thiuram disulphide (IX) was prepared by the oxidation of N,N'-ethyl-

phenylammonium N-ethylphenyl dithiocarbamate with iodine⁵.

IX (10 g) on pyrolysis at 180-210° afforded carbon disulphide which distilled out first (about 2 ml). On raising the temperature to 260-80°, a yellow oily liquid started coming out. TLC of the oil using benzene afforded four spots. A spot with R_f 0.68 was identified as due to N,N'-diethyl-N,N'-diphenyl thiuram sulphide(X) by comparison with an authentic sample prepared by the action of KCN on IX⁶. The spot with R_f 0.257 was identified as due to 1,3-diphenyl-1-ethyl thiocarbamide(XI) by comparison with an authentic sample prepared by the condensation of ethylaniline with phenyl isothiocyanate⁷. Third spot with R_f 0.095 was identified as due to thiocarbanilide.

A part of the residue on TLC in benzene gave identical spots as above with an additional spot due to IX (R_f 0.80). Acetone insoluble part of the residue was elemental sulphur.

Gases evolved during pyrolysis were scrubbed with alkali and absorbed in mercuric acetate solution. TLC of the above solution in propanol^a : triethylamine : water (50 : 25 : 25) gave the spot due to ethylene (R_f 0.713) when developed with diphenyl carbazide.

Pyrolysis of N, N'-dimethyl Thiuram Disulphide (XIII) :

N,N'-Dimethyl thiuram disulphide(XIII) required for pyrolysis was prepared by the oxidation of methylammonium methyl dithiocarbamate with iodine⁸.

Its pyrolysis (XIII ; 10 g) was carried out at 180-200° on an oil bath when carbon disulphide (3 ml) was collected. On increasing the temperature a thick viscous yellow oil started distilling out.

TLC of the distillate using benzene : methanol (70 : 30) gave a spot with R_f 0.35 which was confirmed on comparison with an authentic sample prepared by the action of methylamine on carbon disulphide⁹ as due to methylammonium methyl dithiocarbamate(XVI). The spot with R_f 0.90 was identified as due to 1, 3-dimethyl thiocarbamide(XV) on comparison with an authentic sample prepared by the condensation of methylamine with methyl isothiocyanate⁹. The distillate strongly smelt of methyl isothiocyanate.

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